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INFLUENCE OF DESTINATION IMAGE AND DESTINATION FACILITY ON SATISFACTION OF TOURISTS' NEEDS AMONG TOURISM SITES IN SOUTH EAST, NIGERIA

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Abstract: The aim of the study was to investigate the influence of destination image and destination facility on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. Specific objectives were to: examine the influence of destination image and destination facility on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. A survey research design was used for the study. 41 was total sites in South East, Nigeria. Sample size of study was three hundred and eighty four (384) and convenience sampling technique was adopted for selecting the respondents that completed the questionnaire. After data analysis, it was found that destination image and destination facility had no significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. In the light of the findings, it was concluded that destination image and destination facility had no significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. Therefore, it was recommended that government should try to improve the image of Nigeria in order to attract enough tourists to Nigeria and improve revenues derived from tourism. Government should try to provide adequate security, good road network, constant power supply and other social amenities which have the potential to improve the image of Nigeria and government and attraction site managers such as tourism boards and business entrepreneurs should be supported to provide adequate accommodation, affordable transportation, good restaurants, recreational facilities and retail outlets and other destination facilities that attract visitors to attraction sites in Nigeria.

Keywords: Destination image and destination facility and satisfaction of tourists' needs.

INTRODUCTION

Similarly, Nigeria's tourism receipt situation is not much different from that of Africa. Nigeria's tourism landscape is extremely rich and beautiful for global tourist attraction. The weather, climate, vegetation, quality airspace, sunshine, beautiful scenery, the rocks, waterfalls, captivating beaches, historical relics, rich cultural

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diversity, parks, game reserves, ancient caves, captivating shopping malls, social and religious attractions, friendly people and wildlife are Nigeria's tourism assets. Nigeria's tourism market potential is huge, even though the receipt is quite small (Ejionueme & Nebo, 2021).

Tourism market is of great interest not only to government but also to business entrepreneurs, academics and even tourists due to its current growth potential and size, its potential for continuous growth, its economic contributions in terms of employment, investment, favourable balance of payment, foreign exchange earnings, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Gross National Income (GNI) and its ability to promote mutual understanding among people and nations (Ejionueme & Nebo, 2021).

Nigeria is one of the many countries in the world particularly in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) countries where economic development is badly needed. Despite the high level of crude petroleum export from Nigeria, economic development when expressed in terms of employment level, life expectancy ratio, quality education, per capital income, Gross National Income, Social infrastructure, adequate security, transparency and accountability in governance and general quality of life has continued to remain illusive.

Probably, it is becoming obvious that crude oil, the only product that generates over 80% of Nigeria income could hardly offer the necessary level of economic development required to improve Nigeria's poverty situation. It is now very glaring that crude oil alone cannot improve Nigeria's economic backwardness. Therefore investment in tourism industry appears to be a viable and indispensable strategic option for Nigeria economic development trajectory. However, Nigerian tourism industry appears under-developed. It is in realization of fact that the researcher went into this study to determine the relationship between tourism products' dimensions and satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South-East Nigeria.

Customer satisfaction is one of the greatest tools in steering the growth of the tourism industry (Forozia, *et al*, 2018). In most cases, before a tourist visits a destination, he forms a set of expectations based on previous experience, press reports, advertising, common belief or what people say about the place. He forms a mental picture of the destination through his reasoned and emotional feelings and opinion about the destination's ability to satisfy these needs (Min, *et al*, 2017). When the tourist eventually visits the place, he compares experience he had with his expectations. If the expectations are meet, satisfaction occurs and he is likely to visit the place again otherwise the reverse becomes the case.

Therefore in order to be successfully promoted in the target market, a destination must be favorably differentiated from its competitors. To give the required satisfaction, a tourist destination should have attractive sites, affordable prices, good image, adequate facilities and accessibility. Evidence from the review of related empirical studies would support the conclusion that despite the quantum of studies in tourism particularly in the mainstream literature; significant knowledge-gap still exist with regards to determination of product dimensions that are likely to produce tourists' satisfaction among tourism sites particularly in South-East, Nigerian context. Based on this gap in knowledge, the aim of this research was to determine the influence of destination image, destination facility on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South-East, Nigeria.

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Statement of the Problem

With the disappointing economic performance and the rating of Nigeria as the 103rd poorest nation in the world, calls have been made on both private and public sectors for diversified means of improving Nigeria's economic performance rather than heavy reliance on one-product (oil) export portfolio. These calls have continued to receive a heightened attention based on scholarly advocacy that diversified investments, particularly into the non-oil investment remains a viable and feasible option for Nigeria's hope for sustainable economic development in the 21st century (Anyanwu & Nkamnebe, 2013).

Studies have shown that investments in hospitality and tourism firms are possible ways of solving Nigeria's economic challenges. Findings from previous studies show that Nigeria's tourism industry is grossly underdeveloped although it has great potentials for generating high employment rate, foreign exchange earnings, favorable balance of payment, gross domestic products (GDP) and gross national income (GNI) if adequately tapped (Ejionueme & Nebo, 2021).

This study, therefore, seek to determine which tourism product dimensions (destination sites, destination price, destination images, destination facilities and accessibility of the destination) could possibly yield satisfaction to tourists. It is widely believed that tourists' satisfaction will increase tourism products consumption. This will in turn increase investment interest in the industry and drive the much needed economic development for Nigeria. However, tourists' dissatisfaction is likely to produce low receipt from visits, patronage, investment, foreign exchange, GNI and employment in Nigeria. Ezeokoli and Ayodele (2014), Mubbsher (2014), studies shows that few studied have been done to establish the influence of tourism products' dimensions and satisfaction of tourists' needs in South-East, Nigeria using destination attraction, destination prices, destination images, destination facilities and accessibility as product dimension proxies.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was to examine the influence of tourism products' dimensions on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. Specific objectives include to;

- i. Investigate the extent influence of destination image on the satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria.
- ii. Ascertain the extent influence of destination facility on the satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

This study would be of significance to four major stakeholders. These are tourism managers, policy makers, researchers and tourists.

Tourism Managers: Findings from this study will enable tourism managers to design quality products that will satisfy tourists and draw them to attraction sites in Nigeria.

Policy Makers: This study is important to policy makers in the tourism industry both in the private and public sector as they gain significant insights from the findings of this study. The information on tourism product dimensions and their effect on satisfaction will enable them formulate policies that will attract visitors to tourism sites in Nigeria. This will help generate the much needed economic development in Nigeria in terms of

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employment, foreign exchange earnings, gross domestic products (GDP) and gross national income (GNI) and improvement in the quality of life.

Researchers: This research has implications on future studies as it has potential to determine the effect of tourism products' dimensions on satisfaction of tourists needs among tourism sites in Nigeria. It is useful for academicians to make references and provide additional information to the body of literature in the field of tourism products' dimensions and other similar studies.

Tourists': Findings from this study will enable both tourism managers and policy makers to design quality products that will satisfy tourists in Nigeria.

Scope of the Study

This study is targeted at determining the influence of tourism products' dimensions and satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. States to be covered in this study include: Anambra, Abia, Imo, Ebonyi and Enugu. This study covered five major tourists attraction sites in the Eastern region of Nigeria namely: Ogbunike Cave in Anambra State, Oguta Lake in Imo State, Ojukwu Bunker in Abia State, Onicha Salt Lake in Ebonyi State and Ajali Water falls in Enugu State. The unit of analysis consists of tourists' who had visited any of the attraction sites used in this study. The products' dimensions that covered in the study include: destination image and destination facility were used as predictor variables while satisfaction of tourists' needs was used as dependent variable.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Destination Image

Tasci *et al.*, (2017), "destination image is an interactive system of thoughts, opinions, feelings, visualizations, and intentions toward destination". Chi and Qu (2018) define destination image as an individual's mental representation of the knowledge, feelings, and overall perception of a particular destination.

Destination Facility

These are elements within the destination, or linked to it, which make it possible for visitors to stay and in other ways enjoy and participate in the attractions. They include: accommodation units such as hotels, holiday villages, apartments, villas, campsites, bars and cafes ranging from fast food to luxury restaurants. Transportation at the destinations which include: taxi, coaches, car rentals, cycle hire (and ski lifts in snow destinations). Sports/activity which include: ski schools, sailing schools, golf clubs. Other facilities include: shops, travel agents, souvenirs, camping supplies. Other services: hairdressing, information services, equipment rental, tourism police. For some of these elements, the distinction between attractions and facilities may be blurred, for example, a hotel may well become an attraction in its own right and a prime reason for selecting a destination. Nevertheless, its primary function of providing accommodation and services remains clear (Ejionueme & Nebo, 2021).

Satisfaction of Tourists' Needs

Crompton and Love (2015), define tourists' satisfaction as an emotional state that emerges as a result of an experience with a touristic product. Tourist satisfaction is defined in specific terms as emotional feelings such as happiness, enjoyment, excitements, relaxation, pleasurable experiences tourists'' enjoy when they visit

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attraction sites or their destinations (Bruhn & Grund, 2016). Tourist satisfaction is defined as the level of one's feelings after comparing perceived performance or results compared with expectations (Kotler, 2012).

Conceptual Framework

Based on the above discussions that have been found from the reviewing of the previous literature, two significant products dimensions can be considered. Consequently, the present study proposes the following conceptual framework (Figure 2.1) for further analysis after reviewing numerous recent previous literatures. The conceptual framework is presented in figure 2.1 below

Figure 2.1: Conceptual framework showing the relationship between destination image, destination facility and satisfaction of tourists'.

Source: Adapted from Ejionueme and Nebo (2021). Marketing Technique in Tourism and Hospitality Industry, Enugu: Rhyce Kerex Publishers.

Theoretical Framework

Mehradian-Russel Stimulus-Response Theory

The study was anchored on Mehradian-Russel Stimulus-Response Theory. This theory holds that “feelings determine how people will respond to environment. It states that the conscious and unconscious perception and interpretation of the environment influence how people feel. People’s feelings in turn determine their responses to that environment.

Figure 2.2: Mehrabian-Russel Stimulus-Response Theory

The above theory shows that environmental stimuli which in this study are attraction sites, destination facilities and accessibility to the destinations all can affect tourists’ feelings or mood. Consumer mood state or feelings are expressed in various forms such as happiness, pleasure, confidence, joy, excitement, anger, frustration, anxiety, fear, depression, shame, guilt etc. consumer feelings will determine response behaviour to the environment which may be approach or avoidance. Approach behaviour means that the customer feels good about the environment and this will result in business patronage while avoidance means that the customer dislikes the environment and may likely depart without buying anything. The implication of this theory to

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tourism marketing is that managers of these firms should ensure that the physical environment elements such as interior decorations, exterior facilities, and employees corporate identity are designed to trigger favourable consumer feelings or mood states. Good feelings are likely to produce favourable purchase response (approach) (Ejionueme & Nebo, 2021).

Empirical Review

Chang (2020) found the demographic variables to impact tourist behaviour. Thus, it is evident from the literature that most studies have focused the impact of demographic variables on tourist visit intention but there is a lack of research pertaining to impact of demographic variables on tourist revisit intention.

Yulia, Dyah and Yuni (2020) studied effect of attraction, the quality of destination, motivation, and satisfaction of intention to revisit on heritage destination pembangunan nasional in Veteran Yogyakarta. This study aims to examine the intention to revisit the model of heritage tourism in Yogyakarta. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling with a total of 250 respondents. Data analysis techniques used the AMOS Structural Equation Modeling. The results showed that the intention to revisit the model was acceptable. It was further explained that attractiveness, destination quality, tourist motivation and tourist satisfaction had a positive influence on the intention to return to tourism heritage in the Special Region of Yogyakarta.

Majid, Reihaneh and Hoda (2020) studied the effect of destination image on tourist satisfaction, intention to revisit and WOM in Iran. The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship among destination image, overall image, tourism Satisfaction, intention to revisit recommend in the foursquare that is a social media for sharing information . The purpose of this research is applied and descriptive. The sample of this study includes of domestic and foreign users of Foursquare. According to the results, all dimensions of Destination image have significant and positive effect on overall image and overall image has significant and positive effect on satisfaction and intention to revisit destination and Word of Mouth in Foursquare.

For instance, Zhang and Huang (2022) found the impact of demographic variable on tourist visit intention behaviour to be significant. Socio economic background of the tourist was found to have a significant impact on tourist intention to visit a destination.

Mustafa and Burhanettin (2023) conducted a study on the mediating role of memorable tourism experience on tourist behavior in Turkey. This study aims to determine the effect of destination image on the intention to recommend memorable tourism experiences of tourists participating in organized tours. In this context, the relationships between the variables of destination image, memorable tourism experience, tourist satisfaction and intention to recommend were examined in the research process. Quantitative research methods were used in the study. A questionnaire was preferred as the data collection tool. The population of the research consists of individuals living in Türkiye and having previous experience in organized tours. It has been revealed that the destination image has a positive effect on tourist satisfaction, memorable tourism experience and intention to recommend.

Niloufar and Zahra (2023) conducted study on the role of e-CRM in facilitating tourism destination selection) case study: tehran travel agencies) in tourism marketing in Iran. Survey research design was used. The present study has been conducted through qualitative methods to provide a model explaining the role of ECRM in

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facilitating destination selection. Therefore, the grounded theory method and a non probabilistic purposive sampling were used to determine the study sample. The study revealed that grounded theory methods tools such as data fragmentation, open coding, and axial coding led to identifying six main categories of causal conditions, subject-oriented, contextual or environmental conditions, intervening conditions, strategies and consequences.

Pichsinee, Ann and Timothy (2023) studied the role of slow food in destination image development in China. This paper explores how the slow food concept has a vital role in making tourist trips more fun and healthier at the same time. It shows how to develop a slow food destination image. A qualitative approach using in-depth interviews was employed, and Chiang Mai, Thailand was selected as the study area. A total of 29 tourists were interviewed. Content analysis was used to analyze data. The findings revealed three components for developing a slow food destination image: (a) functional attributes, referring to five aspects: environment, authentic food, slow food community, local facilitators, and service quality; (b) psychological attributes, comprising slow food logo and signs, and value perception; and (c) unique attributes, seeking uniqueness and creating events/festivals related to the slow food concept, especially the concept of a good, clean, and fair event.

Akhmad and Suyoto (2023) conducted study on influence of service quality and hospital image on revisit intention through word of mouth on inpatient services at the Ibnu Sina Regional General Hospital in Gresik District. This study aims to analyze service quality and hospital image affect revisit intention through word of mouth at ibnu sina Gresik hospital. This research uses quantitative methods with 180 respondents consisting of patients and employees who work at ibnu sina Gresik hospital. The results of this study indicated that there is an effect of service quality on revisit intention through word of mouth, and there is also an effect of hospital image on revisit intention through word of mouth at ibnu sina Gresik hospital.

Gaps in Empirical Review

Attraction sites: This study covered five major attraction sites in the South-Eastern state of Nigeria which were not covered in other similar studies. The attraction sites that were given attention in this study include: Ogbunike cave in Anambra state, Oguta Lake in Imo state, Ojukwu Bunker in Abia state, Onicha salt Lake in Ebonyi state and Ajali Waterfalls in Enugu state. These attraction sites were not given attention in other similar studies. **Period of study:** Evidence from the renew of past related work shows that the oldest work was done in 1997 while the latest was done in 2024. Few were done in 2024 representing the year the present study was conducted.

METHODOLOGY

A survey design was the specific design that the researcher employed. The advantage of this design is that data can be collected less expensively and within a short time. Primary data refer to original data collected basically for the purpose of the study. Primary sources of data were used in this study by means of structured questionnaire. A total of 41 attraction sites exist in the South-Eastern State of Nigeria. As a result, the population of study comprised all the actual visitors aged 18 years and older who had visited any of the 41 attraction sites located in South-Eastern Nigeria in the last five years from their book records. The census of the actual visitors to these attraction sites was not available, therefore, the population of the study is deemed unknown or infinite while sample size was 384 with help of Topman's formula. Convenience sampling

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technique was adopted for selecting the respondents that completed the questionnaire since sampling frame was not available. Structured questionnaire was adopted for the collection of data from tourists’ who had visited any of the attraction sites in the five South-Eastern States, Nigeria. The analyses of data were subjected to simple statistical treatment to be organized and presented in tables and percentages. The questionnaire responses were grouped into various categories and entered in the SPSS version 20 software to facilitate analysis using descriptive statistics. Frequency distribution tables were introduced to summarize the data from the respondents. The data expressed in scale. Data were presented in tables, percentages, mean and standard deviation. For the 5-point Likert scale questions (SA-SD), the scale and decision rule stated below were employed in analyzing the data.

Decision Rule

If Mean \geq 3.0, the respondents agree

If mean $<$ 3.0, the respondents disagree

Regression Test

Regression analysis was used to test the five hypotheses to determine the nature, and strength of the research variables.

Fomula for regression

$$Y_i = f(X_i \beta) + e_i$$

X = dependent variable

F = function

X₁ = independent variable

β = coefficient

e_i = error terms

Tests of Hypothesis

Test of Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: Destination image does not have significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists’ needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria.

H₀₁: Destination image has significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists’ needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria.

Table 1: ANOVA of the Regression Model

Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sign (P-Value)
Regression	34.351	3	6.319	-5.158	0.211
Residual	214.787	343	.855		
Total	213.238	346			

Source: Extracted from SPSS Version 25

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Table 2: Estimated Regression of the Model

Model	Coefficient	Std. error	t	Sign (P-Value)
Constant	0.157	0.391	3.3173	0.211
Destination images	0.177	0.271	3.269	0.211

The descriptive analysis in table 1 and 2, where combined in testing hypothesis one. The result of the linear regression analysis carried out on the interaction between destination image (independent variable) and satisfaction of tourists’ needs (dependent variable) is presented in table 1 and 2 above using Fisher’s (F) test and probability (P) value as the decision criteria. The Fisher’s test value presented in table 1 above with F- value of -5.158 and P value of 0.211 ($P > 0.05$) at 5% level of significance indicate that destination image has no significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists’ needs. Based on this we reject the alternate hypothesis and accept null which states that destination image has no significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists’ needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. The result of the coefficient in table 2 shows that a 1% negative change in destination image will decrease 17.7% in tourists’ satisfaction.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Destination facilities do not have significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists’ needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria.

H₀₂: Destination facilities have significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists’ needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria.

Table 3: ANOVA of the Regression Model

Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sign (P-Value)
Regression	34.351	3	6.319	-5.358	0.330
Residual	214.787	343	.855		
Total	213.238	346			

Source: Extracted from SPSS Version 25

Table 4: Estimated Regression of the Model

Model	Coefficient	Std. error	t	Sign (P-Value)
Constant	0.257	0.491	3.4173	0.330
Destination facility	0.277	0.371	3.369	0.331

Fitness Model of the Variables

The descriptive analysis in table 3 and 4, where combined in testing hypothesis two. The result of the linear regression analysis carried out on the interaction between destination facilities (independent variable) and satisfaction of tourists’ needs (dependent variable) is presented in table 3 and 4 above using Fisher’s (F) test and probability (P) value as the decision criteria, the Fisher’s test value presented in table 4 above with F- value of -5.358 and P value of 0.330 ($P > 0.05$) at 5% level of significance indicate that destination facilities has no significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists’ needs. Based on this we reject the alternate hypothesis and accept null which states that destination facilities has no significant positive influence on satisfaction of

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tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. The result of the coefficient in table 4 shows that a 1% negative change in destination image will decrease 2.24% in tourists' satisfaction.

Discussion of Findings

The result of hypothesis one shows that there was no significant positive influence of destination image on satisfaction of tourist needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. This is in agreement with the study of Patcharaporn (2018) who examined the impact of destination image on value, satisfaction, and loyalty: moderating effects of tourists' characteristics and involvement in Malaysia. This study investigated the effect of destination image on perceived destination value, satisfaction and destination loyalty. The findings indicate that destination image has significant effects on perceived value, satisfaction and loyalty. The results also reveal that the strength of the effects do not depend on tourists' gender or material status; however they do depend on tourists' age, income, and level of involvement.

The result of hypothesis two shows that destination facility have no significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourist needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. This is not in the same agreement with the study of Nurcahyo, Fitriyani and Hudda (2017) on the influence of facility and service quality towards customer satisfaction and its impact on customer loyalty in Borobudur Hotel in Jakarta. This research was aimed at determining the influence of the facilities, the quality of service to customer satisfaction and its impact on customer loyalty in Borobudur Hotel in Jakarta. Data collection were done by distributing questionnaires directly to 360 customers in Borobudur Hotel, Jakarta. The analysis technique used was path analysis. The results of this research indicate that the facilities, service quality, and customer satisfaction significantly affect customer loyalty variables simultaneously or partially.

Summary of Findings

After data analysis, the following findings were made:

- i. Destination image had no significant negative influence on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria (f sat -5.158, pv 0.211>0.05).
- ii. Destination facility had no significant negative influence on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria (f sat -5.358, pv 0.331>0.05).

Conclusion

Based on the findings we concluded that destination image and destination facility had no significant positive influence on satisfaction of tourists' needs among tourism sites in South East, Nigeria. It was also concluded that destination images and destination facilities were very poor and do not satisfy the needs of in-bound and out-bound tourists' in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Having analyzed, discussed and interpreted the data collected in this study, the author therefore recommends the following:

- i. Government should try to improve the image of Nigeria in order to attract enough tourists to Nigeria and improve revenues derived from tourism. Government should try to provide adequate security, good road

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network, constant power supply and other social amenities which have the potential to improve the image of Nigeria.

ii. Government and attraction site managers such as tourism boards and business entrepreneurs should be supported to provide adequate accommodation, affordable transportation, good restaurants, recreational facilities and retail outlets and other destination facilities that attract visitors to attraction sites in Nigeria.

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